

Tailoring preference-based food recommendation for diabetic patients

M. J. Barranco* and R. Yera and L. Martínez

Computer Science Department, University of Jaén, Jaén, Spain

**barranco@ujaen.es*

Food recommendation is currently becoming an area of special interest regarding its high impact in the end users. In this direction, for individuals with non-communicable diseases such as diabetes, a tailored food recommendation according to the user's preferences and needs and the available nutritional knowledge could be derived to relevant benefits regarding the importance of an appropriate diet in such disease. The current contribution presents then a novel preference-based food recommendation approach tailored to diabetic patients. An experimental analysis taking as base the USDA database, suggests that in this context it is reachable a balance between the sugar levels and the overall preferences of the generated menus.

Keywords: food recommendation; diabetes; user preferences.

1. Introduction

In the context of e-health, the recommendation of dietary choices is gaining prominence as a significant advisory scenario, considering its close connection to non-communicable diseases and the concept of personalized nutrition¹. Personalized nutrition is characterized as tailored healthy eating guidance based on individual factors such as genetic data, personal health status, lifestyle, nutrient intake, and phenotypic data². Due to the expenses associated with managing genetic data, recent research efforts have intensely focused on handling alternative data sources, leading to the proposal of various computational solutions.

Specifically addressing diabetes, numerous studies have demonstrated that adopting more favorable dietary patterns is linked to lower glycemic load in older adults³. Moreover, low-carbohydrate, Mediterranean, and high-protein diets have been recommended as effective in enhancing various cardiovascular risk markers in individuals with diabetes, warranting consideration in the overall diabetes management strategy⁴. Consequently, a tailored personalized nutrition approach in this context not only contributes

directly to patient safety but also holds global significance. Diabetes is a prevalent global health crisis, estimated to incur an annual cost of US\$827 billion. In 2021, it was reported that 537 million adults worldwide were living with diabetes ^a.

Despite numerous efforts in recent years concentrating on the creation of recommendations for healthy food, the motivation for this current research work within the framework of existing knowledge stems from the observed absence of comprehensive approaches for food recommendation tailored to the domain of diabetes. As recently pointed out by Yera et al. ⁵ in a recent survey on this topic, it is necessary a better exploitation of the knowledge domain for proposing computational solutions in this scenario, and in addition it is necessary a larger exploitation of the user preferences in the whole recommendation process.

The current work is focused on these two directions, by tailoring a preference-based food recommendation model, to be used in the diabetes domain. Specifically, our goal is to exploit medical criteria used for managing nutrition in diabetic patients to accomplish our objective.

The contribution is structured as follows. Section 2 presents a brief background on food recommendation for diabetes patients. Section 3 discusses our approach for generating tailored menu recommendations for the diabetic patients. Section 4 illustrates the performed experiments. Section 5 concludes the contribution.

2. Background

The generation of food recommendations for diabetic patients has been a research goal that have attracted attention in the last few years. Yera et al. ⁵ identifies four groups of works focused on this objective:

- Semantic-driven methodologies, encompassing those that involve the integration of various forms of semantic knowledge management ⁶.
- Approaches centered around optimization, which aim to incorporate methods utilizing restriction-based or optimization-based models for the generation of food recommendations ⁵.
- Approaches based on rules and classifications, presenting a diverse range of works incorporating techniques such as classification, mul-

^a<https://www.makingdiabeteseasier.com/es/diabetes-explicada/diabetes/panorama-mundial-diabetes-2021>

ticriteria decision-making, fuzzy inference, or production rules to support food recommendations⁷.

- Interaction-centric approaches, characterized by a shared attribute of engaging in an interactive process with users to derive final recommendations⁵.

Beyond the previous efforts done by the research community in this direction, Yera et al.⁵ pointed out the following shortcomings:

- The lack of a a cohesive framework intended to serve as a foundation for subsequent research in generating nutritional recommendations for individuals with diabetes.
- The scarce utilization of the related knowledge domain to suggest computational solutions in this context.
- The necessity of a heightened integration of user preferences in the generation of recommendations.

Taking account this scenario, the current contribution attempts to performing the first steps towards the development of preference-based food recommendation approach, tailored to the diabetes domain.

3. Generating tailored menu recommendations for diabetic patients

The overall objective of the current work is the development of computational approaches focused on reaching improved menu recommendations regarding their composition, tailored for diabetic patients, and keeping a high overall preference with them.

As starting point it is taken the previously proposed model focused on menu recommendation based on user preferences and nutritional information developed by Yera et al.¹, which is not focused on any specific disease:

$$\text{Maximize } \sum_{k \in A} w_k f_k \quad (1)$$

s.t.

$$|\sum_j (nt_{kj} * f_k) - b_j| \leq \alpha, \text{ for each nutrient } 1, 2, 3, \dots, J$$

$$\sum_{k \in G_a} f_k = n_{G_a}, \text{ for each } n_{G_a} \in \{n_{G_1}, n_{G_2}, n_{G_3}^l, n_{G_4}^l, n_{G_5}^l, n_{G_3}^d, n_{G_4}^d, n_{G_5}^d, n_{G_6}\},$$

being G_a the groups in Table 1.

The menu recommendation generation in this context is driven by an objective function (based on the user preferences), and two group of restrictions based on a) nutrients requirements (proteins, carbohydrates and lipids), and b) diversity of foods from different groups, that should contain the menu (milk, cereals, meat, fruits, etc).

According to Yera et al.¹, this model is focused on:

- (1) **Maximizing the sum of preferences w_i of all the foods i included in the plan.** Herein, w_i depends on the frequent of consumption of the food i , as well as how recent was its last consumption (Equation 2).

$$w_k = \frac{N_k}{N} (e^{\theta(\frac{t_c - t_k}{t_c})} - 1) \quad (2)$$

- (2) **Verifying that the nutrients of the generated plan are very close to the required nutrients for the current user profile.** This goal is verified by assuring that for each nutrient, the absolute difference between the required amount (b_j) and the final amount $\sum_j (nt_{kj} * f_k)$, is always under a threshold α .
- (3) **Guaranteeing that the generated plan fills the menu templates presented in Table 1.** This table defines several groups of foods, considered in the composition of the generated menus.

Table 1. The template for the daily meal plan

Breakfast	
n_{G_1}	foods of group G_1 (Milk, yogurts)
n_{G_2}	foods of group G_2 (Breakfast cereals)
n_{G_6}	foods of group G_6 (Fruits)
Lunch	
$n_{G_3}^l$	foods of group G_3 (Proteins)
$n_{G_4}^l$	foods of group G_4 (Carbohydrates)
$n_{G_5}^l$	foods of group G_5 (Vegetables)
n_{G_6}	foods of group G_6 (Fruits)
Dinner	
$n_{G_3}^d$	foods of group G_3 (Proteins)
$n_{G_4}^d$	foods of group G_4 (Carbohydrates)
$n_{G_5}^d$	foods of group G_5 (Vegetables)
n_{G_6}	foods of group G_6 (Fruits)

Based on this framework, the goal of the current work is to tailoring

the screened menu recommendation task, for the context of the diabetic patients.

To accomplish this task, primarily we have adopted the following premise that is supported by the related literature, as explained below.

Premise: *Reducing sugar consumption benefits diabetic patients.* It has been identified that diabetics should control in a special way the consumption of sugar (rapid-absorption carbohydrates), replacing them by low-absorption carbohydrates⁸⁻¹⁰.

Related to this goal, the literature has identified that:

- Fructose consumed as “free fructose” (i.e., naturally occurring in foods such as fruit, (that also contain fiber) may result in better glycemic control compared with isocaloric intake of sucrose or starch⁸.
- Gray et al.⁸ also suggest the replacing of high GI (glycemic index) foods with low GI foods; as well as decreasing the consumption of sugary foods like cookies, cakes, candy, and soft-drinks.
- People with diabetes and those at risk are advised to avoid sugar-sweetened beverages (including fruit juices) in order to control glycemia and weight⁸.
- Although all carbohydrates can be incorporated into carbohydrate counting, for good health, carbohydrates from vegetables, fruits, whole grains, legumes, and dairy products take priority over other carbohydrate sources, especially those that contain added fats, sugars, or sodium⁹.

Based on this statement that supports the tailoring of the food recommendation considering preferences and nutritional knowledge for the diabetes domain, we screen the following issue:

Can we obtain menu recommendations in which sugar restrictions on the daily menu are applied with no (or minimal) reduction in user preference?

To solve this issue, we will consider a different objective function in relation to the formerly proposed model, focused on reducing the overall amount of sugar in the generated menu, without affecting the preference w_k of the user over the generated menu.

This objective function (Equation 3) is represented through a convex combination of the preference w_k of the user over the item k , and the amount of sugar that this item has. In the referred equation, such amount is represented through a normalize way by taking as reference the maximum amount of sugar that could be associated to an item.

$$Max \sum_{k \in A} \left((1 - \beta)w_k + \beta \frac{compo_{max}^{sugar} - compo_k^{sugar}}{compo_{max}^{sugar}} \right) f_k \quad (3)$$

4. Experiments

The evaluation of the presented framework uses the USDA National Nutrient Database ^b, which characterizes each food according to their macronutrients and micronutrients. We link each food in this dataset with a food group of the menu template illustrated in Table 1, being considered six groups: 1) Milk, yogurt; 2) Breakfast cereals; 3) Proteins; 4) Carbohydrates, 5) Vegetables, and 6) Fruits.

For testing the proposed model, different types of user profiles are built taking into account a higher or lower sugar consumption. Three types are particularly built: 1) *Profile₈₀*, with users with a daily consumption of up to 80mg of sugar, 2) *Profile₆₀*, with users consuming up to 60mg, and 3) *Profile₄₀*, with users consuming up to 40mg. For each category 500 users profiles are created, each one with 10 associated menus generated in a random way satisfying the sugar-related constraints.

Based in this setting, we generate a menu considering the formerly presented model (Equation 1) and assuming the objective function presented in Equation 3. We consider several values of β in the range [0,1]. For the generated menus it will be considered as evaluation criteria: 1) the overall preference over the generated menu, and 2) the amount of sugar in the menu.

In the first case, Figure 1 illustrates how the overall user preference on the generated menu evolved with different values of β , considering the three mentioned types of users respectively for the subfigures a), b), and c). Here the X-axis illustrates the sugar restriction value (lower values mean greater restriction) and the Y-axis the preferences of the users.

Figure 2 follows a similar purpose and structure, with the particularity that in this case the Y-axis illustrates the actual amount of sugar in the generated menus.

The experiment shows that as the restriction on sugar in the optimization formula increases (i.e., as the value of x decreases), both overall preference and the actual amount of sugar in the menu decrease. However, a

^b<https://data.nal.usda.gov/dataset/composition-foods-raw-processed-prepared-usda-national-nutrient-database-standard-referen-10>

Fig. 1. Evolving of sugar restrictions in relation to the overall preferences of the generated menus. a) *Profile₈₀* case. b) *Profile₆₀* case. c) *Profile₄₀* case.

Fig. 2. Evolving of sugar restrictions in relation to actual amount of sugar in the generated menus. a) *Profile₈₀* case. b) *Profile₆₀* case. c) *Profile₄₀* case.

greater decrease in the actual amount of sugar is observed than in the value of overall preference, particularly when the increase in restriction is slight. For example, in *profile₈₀* (users who typically consume 80g of sugar daily), applying a value of $\beta = 0.4$ in the formula, we have a reduction of 30g of sugar per day, approximately, while only losing one-tenth in user preference value.

5. Conclusions

The current research work has been focused on the exploration of a novel preference-based food recommendation approach tailored to the diabetes patients. As main contribution, the proposal suggest the reaching of an optimization criterion over the generated menus, that balances the sugar level and the overall user preferences. Several experimental setting were

explored, identifying the peculiarities of each scenario. Future works will be focused on a more extensive exploitation of the medical knowledge in this scenario.

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